

STUDENT ENGAGEMENT AND GOAL ORIENTATION, RESILIENCE: A STUDY ON SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper was to examine the relationship between goal orientation, resilience, and student engagement of junior college students. Random sample of 1067 government secondary school students were selected for the study. Standardized instruments were used to collect the data from a sample of students. The student engagement scale constructed by Lam, Wong, Jimerson, Kikas, Shin, et.al (2014), and Resilience scale developed by Connor-Davidson (2003), Goal Orientation Scale developed by Button, Mathieu, Zajac (2016) were used in the present study. The study used a correlational research design. Results revealed that there is a positive and significant relationship between goal orientation, resilience, and student engagement of secondary school students. This paper explains the significance of this result and its ramifications.

Keywords: Goal Orientation, Resilience, Student Engagement, Junior college students.

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1.0 Introduction

When students are learning or being taught, they exhibit varying degrees of attentiveness, curiosity, interest, optimism, and passion. This extends to their drive to study and advance in their education. Student engagement is crucial because it has a direct impact on academic achievement, retention rates, and overall student success. When students are engaged, they are more likely to develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter, retain information, and apply their knowledge effectively. Engaged students also tend to have higher levels of satisfaction and enjoyment in their educational experiences.

The present study is based on three major closely intertwined concepts. These concepts consist of goal orientations, resilience, and student engagement. This chapter discusses the overview of these concepts along with related research in these areas conducted both in the western world.

Affective Engagement: Affective engagement refers to students' feelings about learning (Connell & Wellborn, 1991; Skinner & Belmont, 1993) and the school they attend (Finn, 1989; Voelkl, 1997). Students may feel bored or interested in learning activities.

Behavioural Engagement: Behavioural Engagement refers to effort and persistence in schoolwork (Birch & Ladd, 1997) and participation in extracurricular activities (Finn, Pannozzo, & Voelkl, 1995).

Cognitive Engagement: Cognitive engagement refers to the cognitive strategies that students adopt and employ during the learning process (Walker, Greene, & Mansell, 2006).

1.1 Goal Orientation

Goal orientation refers to an individual's psychological mindset or disposition towards their goals. It involves the underlying beliefs, attitudes, and approaches individuals adopt when pursuing and striving to achieve their objectives. There are two primary types of goal orientations: Performance goal orientation leads individuals to gauge the difficulty of the task, consider their chances of success, and think about how their performance is likely to compare to that of others. A learning goal orientation leads the individual to focus on the task at hand and to develop adaptive task strategies.

1.2 Resilience

Resilience refers to the ability of an individual, community, or system to bounce back, recover, and adapt in the face of adversity, challenges, or stressful situations. It is the capacity to withstand and overcome difficult circumstances, setbacks, or failures, and to continue functioning and growing despite them. Resilience is not about avoiding or eliminating stress, hardships, or difficult experiences, but rather about developing the skills, mindset, and support systems to navigate and recover from them effectively. It involves being able to cope with change, manage emotions and stress, solve problems, maintain a positive outlook, and maintain a sense of purpose and direction. Resilience can be cultivated and strengthened through various means, such as developing strong social connections and support networks, practicing self-care and self-regulation techniques, fostering a growth mindset, setting realistic goals, seeking help when needed, and learning from past experiences. It is a valuable quality that can help individuals and communities thrive in the face of adversity and improve overall well-being.

2.0 Review of Literature

Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris (2004) analyse the concept of school engagement and its potential impact on student learning and resilience. They explore different dimensions of engagement, including behavioural, emotional, and cognitive aspects, and examine how

engagement affects student outcomes. The review highlights the importance of fostering engagement in educational settings.

Harackiewicz, Barron, Carter, Lehto, & Elliot, (1997). This study explores the relationship between performance goal orientation and student engagement in the college classroom. The researchers investigate the predictors and consequences of achievement goals, examining how goal orientation influences student interest and academic performance. The findings shed light on the complex interplay between performance goals and student engagement.

Midgley, Kaplan, and Middleton, M. (2001). This study examines the effects of learning goal orientation on student engagement. It explores how performance-approach goals, which focus on achieving favourable judgments from others, can influence engagement. The study discusses the potential benefits and costs associated with performance-approach goals and provides insights into their impact on student engagement.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The present research study is a quantitative research study which is based on descriptive research perspective. The research aimed to explore the relation among goal orientation and student engagement of the junior college students.

3.2 Sample:

Sample consisted of secondary school students (N=1067) between the age range of 16 to 19 years; Random sampling method was used for the sample selection, from Government secondary schools located in Hyderabad District of Telangana State.

3.3 Measures:

3.3.1 Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC)

Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale developed by Conner-Davidson (2003). This scale has comprised twenty-five items. The response format is a five point -factor scale ranging from not true at all (1) to true nearly all the time (5). For all twenty-five items giving a range from 25 to 250. A total score is calculated, higher scores on this scale indicate greater resilience. This scale has reliability and validity.

3.3.2 Goal Orientation Scale

Goal Orientation Scale was developed by Button, Mathieu, Zajac (2016). This instrument has two sub scales that is performance goal orientation and learning goal orientation. Performance goal orientation scale was assessed with ten items. Responses to the items in this scale were

made on a five-point Likert type format ranging from, (1) Strongly Disagree to (5) strongly Agree. This scale comprises of ten items exhibited a Cronbach’s alpha of .76. High agreement with these items indicates a strong desire to obtain favourable judgments one’s competencies or conversely, a desire to avoid negative judgments of one’s competencies (i.e., a strong performance goal orientation). Low agreement suggests little concern for performing better than others or making errors (i.e., a weak performance goal orientation). Learning goal orientation was assessed with ten items.

These items were also rated on a five-point Likert type response format ranging from, (1) Strongly Disagree to (5) strongly Agree. This scale comprises of ten items exhibited a Cronbach’s alpha was .79. Strong agreement with these items indicates a strong desire to perform challenging work, learn new skills, and develop alternative strategies when working on a difficult task (i.e., a strong learning goal orientation). Low agreement suggests little concern for mastering tasks or gaining competency (i.e., a weak learning goal orientation). This scale has reliability and validity.

3.3.3 Student Engagement Scale

The student engagement scale constructed by Lam, Wong, Jimerson, Kikas, Shin, et.al (2014) were used in the present study. The scale has 33 items, divided in three dimensions namely: Affective Engagement, Behavioural Engagement and Cognitive Engagement. The Likert scale for the affective and behavioural engagement subscales is the followings: (1) strongly disagree, (2) disagree, (3) Neutral (4) agree, and (5) strongly agree. The Likert scale for the Cognitive Engagement subscale is the followings: (1) Never, (2) Rarely, (3) Sometimes, (4) Often, and (5) Always. Affective Engagement subscale has one reversed item (5) and Behavioural Engagement also has three reversed items (5, 6, 7). The mean of the item scores on each subscale was used to indicate student engagement in the relevant dimension. High scores indicated high levels of student engagement.

4.0 Results and Discussion

To examine the relationship between goal orientation, resilience and student engagement of junior college students, a product moment correlation coefficient was computed between goal orientation, resilience and student engagement of junior college students, the results obtained are presented in table 1& 2.

Table 1 : Means, Standard Deviations and Correlation Coefficients between Goal Orientation and student engagement

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
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1. Affective engagement	37.747	5.1029				
2. Behavioural engagement	46.715	5.9139	.590**			
3. Cognitive Engagement	47.508	6.8817	.383**	.471**		
4. Performance Goal Orientation	40.220	5.3413	.272**	.320**	.320**	
5. Learning Goal Orientation	42.221	5.1252	.492**	.517**	.528**	.472**

****p<0.001**

From table 1 it can be observed that the correlation coefficient computed between goal orientation (performance, Learning) total score and the student engagement (affective, behavioural, and cognitive engagement) is positive and found to be significant ($p<.01$). It can be also observed from table 1 that the goal orientation (performance, Learning) is positively related with the different dimensions of student engagement. These results indicates that there is a significant positive relationship between goal orientation (performance, Learning) and student engagement of junior college students. these results derived from studies (Wolters, Yu, & Pintrich; 1996, Bong, 2001).

4.2 Resilience and Student Engagement

To examine the relationship between resilience and student engagement of junior college students, the product moment correlation coefficient between resilience and student engagement score were computed, the results obtained are presented in table 2.

Table 2 : Means, Standard Deviations and Correlation Coefficients between Resilience and Student Engagement

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4
1. Affective engagement	37.747	5.1029				
2. Behavioural engagement	46.715	5.9139	.590**			
3. Cognitive Engagement	47.508	6.8817	.383**	.471**		
4. Resilience	101.227	13.0431	.342**	.378**	.516**	

****p<0.001**

From table 2 it can be observed that the correlation coefficient computed between resilience total score and the student engagement (affective, behavioural, and cognitive engagement) is positive and found to be significant ($p<.01$). It can be also observed from table 2 that the resilience is positively related with the different dimensions of student. These results indicates

that there is a significant positive relationship between resilience and student engagement of junior college students. This study consistent with research results (Martin, and Marsh, 2008).

5.0 Conclusion

The present study required to investigate the relationship among goal orientation, resilience, and student engagement in a sample of secondary school students. Specifically, the main aim was to examine whether goal orientation and resilience was related to their student engagement of senior secondary school students. Findings supported both the correlational and to test the hypotheses. In detail, these results supported Hypothesis 1& 2 is showing positive and significant relationship between goal orientation, resilience, and affective, behavioural, cognitive dimensions of student engagement. It is important to note that student engagement is not a fixed trait and can fluctuate over time. Different students may exhibit varying levels of engagement depending on various factors such as the teaching methods, classroom environment, subject matter, and personal interests. This study confirms the importance of goal orientation, resilience and all three dimensions of student engagement of junior college students.

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